

Nonlinear Control Design Using Exact Linearization for Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator

Muhammad Ali, Feng Guo, and Bei Gou
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering,
North Dakota State University
Fargo, ND 58108

Abstract—The paper presents the ways of modeling and analysis of exactly linearized permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) coupled with boost chopper in wind generation systems. The primary focus of this paper is to use state of art approach for linearizing nonlinear model and to obtain control law. Exact feedback linearization via state feedback algorithm is the basic scheme that has been derived for the PMSG boost convertor nonlinear model.

Index Terms—permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG), Exact feedback linearization, wind system non linear model, Control Law

NOMENCLATURE

I_L	Inductor Current.	
R_s	Resistance of the stator circuit.	
L_s	Stator inductance of stator.	
p_n	Number of pole pairs.	
Φ_{PM}	Useful flux linkage.	
ω_e	Electrical speed of the machine.	
ω_{ref}	Reference electrical speed.	
θ_e	Electrical Angle of rotor.	u Contro Law.
$\Phi_{w_i}^{\bar{D}_i}$	Integral curve for mapping.	v Linear Control Variable.
W	W space.	
X	X space.	
Z	Z space.	

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development in Smart Grid and Renewable Energy has put power system planners in a competitive environment looking for the best possible solution for power system operation and control. Stabilized power system operation is the key feature for power supplying agencies and consumers satisfaction. Among all types of synchronous generators, permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) has its own merits including small size, low moment of inertia, high reliability, no excitation requirement, which is a good choice for wind energy conversion system. PMSG coupled with wind

turbine systems extracts maximum power from the wind by optimal adjustment of shaft speed. This design is used by small variable wind turbine for high controllability generation and stable delivering power.

PMSG with boost convertor model for wind energy system is studies in literature [1]-[4]. The generator section is coupled with rectifier circuits and DC-DC Chopper boost Convertor. Slow dynamic response is reported by authors in [2]-[7] using PI controller for PMSG. Optimal parameter adjustment for best performance in varying conditions is not easy to handle by PI controller and is obtained through hit and trial scheme. Nonlinear control schemes have worked well in the field of power electronics. Authors in [8] used the scheme of hysteresis current control which improved the dynamic performance of the overall system. Later on, sliding mode control topology [9] has been applied on different kinds of converters which enhanced the characteristics features of the proposed model. Modern control strategies have changed the response of the system in terms of stability, reliability, optimal performance and improvement in dynamics. Complex mathematical computations, modeling, analysis and conceptual understanding are required for implementing nonlinear schemes to power converters. Fuzzy logic scheme [10] is implemented for choppers successfully that changed the properties of the nonlinear system when converters are interfaced with it. Model adaptive nonlinear control [11] and robust control [12] have been proven to have better performance for power converters control in contrast to conventional schemes like proportion integral control (PID).

Exact linearization via state feedback transforms a nonlinear system into linear one with all disturbances decoupled from the output either in form of simple approach of linearization, zero dynamics design, disturbance decoupled method, or algorithms of exact linearization. Each scheme involves coordinate transformation from one space to other to completely convert the nonlinear system into Brunovsky normal form. In conventional schemes, the negligence of higher order terms sacrifices the optimal performance and accuracy and limits the

operation within a fixed boundary. A lot of literatures [13]-[18] are available for the implementation of this scheme to different types of energy systems, for example wind, solar, PMSG, doubly fed induction generator, etc. The idea of exact linearization was first presented by Brockett [19]. Necessary and sufficient conditions of multiple input cases for external global linearization were presented by Jakubczyk [20]. Simplified sufficient conditions for exact global linearization was done by Hunt [21].

The paper is divided into four sections. First section illustrates the case of single input single output feedback linearization conditions and concept of lie algebra involved. Second section provides whole mathematical modeling and analysis for PMSG coupled with boost convertor. The third section provides the optimal control law and last section includes the concluding remarks.

II. EXACT LINEARIZATION CONDITIONS FOR SISO SYSTEM

Consider a non-linear affine system as,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{X} &= f(X) + g(X)u \\ y &= h(X) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where X is the state vector such that $X \in R^n$, u is the control variable while f, g are the n dimensional vector fields.

Lie bracket and lie derivative operation performed as:

$$\begin{aligned} ad_f g &= [f, g](X) = \nabla g \cdot f - \nabla f \cdot g \\ ad_f^2 g &= \nabla ad_f g \cdot f - \nabla f \cdot ad_f g \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

.....

$$ad_f^i g = \nabla ad_f^{i-1} g \cdot f - \nabla f \cdot ad_f^{i-1} g$$

Consider lie derivative of scalar function $\lambda(X)$ along $f(X)$ as,

$$L_f \lambda(X) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial \lambda(X)}{\partial x_i} f_i(X) \quad (3)$$

Following are the conditions to be satisfied:

- 1.(a) $L_g L_f^k h(X) = 0, k < r-1, \forall X \in \Omega$
- (b) $L_g L_f^{r-1} h(X) \neq 0$
2. $D = [g \quad ad_f g \quad \dots \quad ad_f^{n-1} g](X), r(D) = n$ (4)
3. Matrix D should be involutive at $X = X^0$

Where $r(D)$ is the rank of the matrix D and n is the degree of the state vector.

III. NONLINEAR MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF PMSG-BOOST CONVERTER

The state space model of PMSG-Boost Convertor [22] is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{I}_L &= k_1 I_L + k_2 \omega_e \sin(\theta_e - 60) + k_3 \\ \dot{\omega}_e &= k_4 I_L \sin(\theta_e - 60) + k_5 \omega_e + k_6 \\ \dot{\theta}_e &= \omega_e \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where ,

$$\begin{aligned} k_1 &= -\frac{2R_s}{2L_s + L}, k_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{3}\Phi_{PM}}{2L_s + L}, k_3 = -\frac{v_{dc}}{2L_s + L} \\ k_4 &= \frac{\sqrt{3}p_n^2 \Phi_{PM}}{J}, k_5 = -\frac{F}{J}, k_6 = \frac{p_n}{J} T_m \\ k_7 &= \frac{v_{dc}}{2L_s + L} \end{aligned}$$

Selecting state variables as,

$$x_1 = I_L, x_2 = \omega_e, x_3 = (\theta_e - 60)$$

Finally, the system equations become,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= k_1 x_1 + k_2 x_2 \sin x_3 + k_3 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= x_2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The vector fields as stated in Eq. (1) is as follows,

$$f(X) = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 x_1 + k_2 x_2 \sin x_3 + k_3 \\ k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$g(X) = \begin{bmatrix} k_7 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, y = h(X) = x_3 \quad (7)$$

Now, applying the procedure for exact linearization algorithm step by step. Since the studied system is a third order affine nonlinear system, performing lie bracket operation as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} ad_f g &= - \begin{bmatrix} k_1 k_7 \\ k_4 k_7 \sin x_3 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ ad_f^2 g &= \begin{bmatrix} k_1^2 k_7 + k_2 k_4 k_7 \sin^2 x_3 \\ k_4 k_7 (-x_2 \cos x_3 + k_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 \sin x_3) \\ k_4 k_7 \sin x_3 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Formation of n linearly independent vector fields $\bar{D}_1, \bar{D}_2, \bar{D}_3$ and selecting necessary scalar functions such that each independent vector field is solved to get simplified model,

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{D}_{11} \\ \bar{D}_{12} \\ \bar{D}_{13} \end{bmatrix} + k_1^{(1)}(X) [g(X)] &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} \bar{D}_{21} \\ \bar{D}_{22} \\ \bar{D}_{23} \end{bmatrix} + k_1^{(2)}(X) [g(X)] + k_2^{(2)}(X) [ad_f g] &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} \bar{D}_{31} \\ \bar{D}_{32} \\ \bar{D}_{33} \end{bmatrix} + k_1^{(3)}(X) [g(X)] + k_2^{(3)}(X) [ad_f g] \\ + k_3^{(3)}(X) [ad_f^2 g] &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$k_1^{(1)}(X) = -\frac{1}{k_7}$$

$$k_1^{(2)}(X) = k_2^{(2)}(X) k_1$$

$$k_2^{(2)}(X) = \frac{1}{k_4 k_7 \sin x_3}$$

$$\bar{D}_1 \in D_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\bar{D}_2 \in D_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\bar{D}_3 \in D_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Defining the mapping and solving set of partial differential equations,

$$F(w_1, w_2, w_3) = \Phi_{w_1}^{\bar{D}_1} \circ \Phi_{w_2}^{\bar{D}_2} \circ \Phi_{w_3}^{\bar{D}_3}, X_0 = [x_{1o} \quad x_{2o} \quad x_{3o}]^T$$

$$F_1(w_1, w_2, w_3) = w_1 + x_{1o} = x_1 \} X = F(W)$$

$$F_2(w_1, w_2, w_3) = w_2 + x_{2o} = x_2 \} X = F(W)$$

$$F_3(w_1, w_2, w_3) = w_3 + x_{3o} = x_3 \} X = F(W)$$

Inverse Mapping F^{-1} becomes, (11)

$$w_1 = x_1 - x_{1o}$$

$$w_2 = x_2 - x_{2o}$$

$$w_3 = x_3 - x_{3o}$$

Derived mapping is calculated as,

$$F_*^{-1}(f) = J_{F^{-1}} f(X) \} X = F(W)$$

$$f^{(0)}(W) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1^{(0)}(W) \\ f_2^{(0)}(W) \\ f_3^{(0)}(W) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$F_*^{-1}(f) = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 x_1 + k_2 x_2 \sin x_3 + k_3 \\ k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Now we derive relations for the coordinate transformation R_{n-1} .

We will perform the coordinate transformation from W space to Z^{n-1} space. Required mapping will be calculated from X space to Z^{n-1} space. Coordinate transformation T is defined as, $T = R_{n-1} F^{-1}$. The relations among the coordinate transformation between W, X, Z is explained in the Fig.1.

Defining the transformation R_i and composite transformation T as,

$$R_1 : z_1^{(1)} = f_2^{(0)} = k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6$$

$$z_2^{(1)} = f_3^{(0)} = x_2$$

$$z_3^{(1)} = w_3 = x_3 - x_{3o}$$

Fig.1. Coordinate transformations between W, X, Z spaces

$$f^{(1)}(W) = J_{R_1} f^{(0)}(W)$$

$$f^{(1)}(W) = \begin{bmatrix} k_4 \sin x_3 (k_1 x_1 + k_2 x_2 \sin x_3 + k_3) \\ + k_5 (k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6) \\ + k_4 x_1 x_2 \cos x_3 \\ k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$R_2 : z_1^{(2)} = f_2^{(1)}(X) = k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6$$

$$z_2^{(2)} = f_3^{(1)}(X) = x_2$$

$$z_3^{(2)} = z_3^{(1)} = x_3 - x_{3o}$$

$$z_1^{(2)} = T_1(X) = k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6$$

$$z_2^{(2)} = T_2(X) = x_2$$

$$z_3^{(2)} = T_3(X) = x_3 - x_{3o}$$

$$f(X) = J_T(X) f(X)$$

$$f(X) = \begin{bmatrix} k_4 \sin x_3 & k_5 & k_4 x_1 \cos x_3 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_1(X) \\ f_2(X) \\ f_3(X) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$f(X) = \begin{bmatrix} k_4 \sin x_3 (k_1 x_1 + k_2 x_2 \sin x_3 + k_3) + k_5 x_2 + k_4 x_1 x_2 \cos x_3 \\ \dot{x}_2 \\ x_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$g(X) = \begin{bmatrix} k_4 k_7 \sin x_3 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Final coordinate transformation $Z = F(X)$ for the conversion of nonlinear system into exactly linear system is,

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 &= w_3 = x_3 - x_{3o} \\ z_2 &= f_3 = x_2 \\ z_3 &= \dot{f}_2 = x_2 = k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Exactly linearized system $X = F^{-1}(Z)$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}_1 &= z_2 \\ \dot{z}_2 &= z_3 \\ \dot{z}_3 &= v \end{aligned}$$

The control law is defined as,

$$\begin{aligned} y &= h(X) = x_3 \\ u &= x_3 = \frac{-f_1(X) + v^*}{g_1(X)} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v^* &= -1.75\omega_n (k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6) + 3.25\omega_n^2 \Delta\omega \\ &+ \omega_n^3 \int \Delta\omega dt \end{aligned}$$

$\Delta\omega = \omega_{ref} - \omega_e$, ω_n is the system natural frequency.

This is a complex equation for the control law involving many terms such as system parameters, generator parameters and certain constants. Each parameter depends upon the type of system used and generator controlled setup. The control law u will make the speed constant of PMSG setup.

Simulation results of the derived nonlinear controller will be presented in future papers.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the state of art control law for the PMSG-Boost convertor for the applications of wind energy systems. Complex nonlinear model is transformed into a linear system thus providing a control law for most controlled wind mechanism. Proposed mechanism is the extension of work presented by A. Isidori in 1985 for the global linearization of nonlinear systems through state feedback. Steps were simple to transform but involves lengthy mathematical stuff and complex understanding.

$$u = \frac{-(k_4 \sin x_3 (k_1 x_1 + k_2 x_2 \sin x_3 + k_3) + k_5 x_2 + k_4 x_1 x_2 \cos x_3) - 1.75\omega_n (k_4 x_1 \sin x_3 + k_5 x_2 + k_6) + 3.25\omega_n^2 \Delta\omega + \omega_n^3 \int \Delta\omega dt}{k_4 k_7 \sin x_3} \quad (17)$$

V. REFERENCES

- [1] J.M.Carrasco, L.G.Franquelo, J.T.Bialasiewicz, E.Galavan, R.C.P. Guisado, M.A.M.Prats, J.I.Leon, N.M.Alfonso, "Power-electronic systems for the grid integration of renewable energy sources: A survey," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol.53, no.4, pp.1002-1016, Aug.2006.
- [2] F.S.dosReis, K.Tan, and S.Islam, "Using PFC for harmonic mitigation in wind turbine energy conversion systems," in *Proc. 30th Annu. Conf. IEEE Ind. Electron. Soc.*, Busan, Korea, Nov.2-6, 2004, pp.3100-3105.
- [3] A.M.Knight and G.E.Petres, "Simple wind energy controller for an expanded operating range," *IEEE Trans. Energy Convers.*, vol.20, no.2, pp.459-466, Jun.2005.
- [4] K.Amei, Y.Takayasu, T.Ohji, and M.sakui, "A maximum power control of wind generator system using a permanent magnet synchronous generator and a boost chopper circuit," in *Proc. Power Convers. Conf.*, Osaka, Japan, Apr.2-5, 2002, pp.1447-1452.
- [5] S.M.Muyeen, R.Takahashi, T.Murata, and J.Tamura, "Transient stability enhancement of variable speed wind turbine driven PMSG with rectifier boost convertor-invertor", in *Proc. 18th Int. Conf. Elect. Mach.*, Vilamoura, Portugal, Sep.6-9, 2008, pp.1-6.
- [6] M.E.Haque, M.Negnevitsky, and K.M.Muttaqi, "A novel control strategy for a variable speed wind turbine with PMSG," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol.46, no.1, pp.331-339, Jan/Feb.2010.
- [7] S.H.Song, S.L.kang, and N.K.Hahm, "Implementation and control of grid connected ac-dc-ac power power convertor for variable speed wind energy conversion system," in *Proc. 18th Annu. Conf. IEEE APEC*, Miami Beach, FL, Feb.9-13, 2003, pp.154-158.
- [8] S.ConcepcionHuerta, P.Alou, J.A.Oliver, O.Garcia, J.a.cobos, and A.M.A-Alfotouh, "Non Linear control for DC-DC convertor based on hysteresis of the Cout current with a frequency loop to operate at constant frequency," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol.58, no.3, pp.1036-1043, Mar.2011.
- [9] S.C.Tan, Y.M.Lai, and C.K.Tse, "A unified approach to the design of PWM based sliding mode voltage controllers for basic dc-dc convertors in Continuous Conduction Mode," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. I, Reg. Papers*, vol.53, no.8, pp.1816-1827, Aug.2006.
- [10] K.Viswanathan, D.Srinivasan, and R.Oruganti, "Design and analysis of SISO fuzzy logic controller for power electronic convertors," in *Proc. FUZZ-IEEE Conf.*, Budapest, Hungary, Jul.25-29, 2004, vol.3, pp.1293-1298, Jul.2011.
- [11] F.Luo and D.S Ma, "Design of digital tri mode adaptive output buck-boost power convertor for high efficient integrated systems," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol.57, no.6, pp.2151-2160, Jun.2010.
- [12] V.Mummadi, "Design of robust digital PID controller for H bridge soft switching boost convertor," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol.58, no.7, pp.2883-2897, Jul.2011.
- [13] J.J.E.Slotine and W.Li, *Applied Non Linear Control*, EnglewoodCliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 1991.
- [14] R.P.Burgos, E.P.Wiechmann, and J.Holtz, "Complex state space modeling and non linear control of active front end convertors," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.* vol.52, no.2, pp.363-377, Apr.2005.
- [15] K.H.Kim and M.J.Youn, "A non linear speed control for a PM synchronous motor using a simple disturbance estimation technique," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol.49, no.3, pp.524-535, Jun.2002.
- [16] H.AbootorabiZarchi, J.Soltani, and G.ArabMarkadeh, "Adaptive Input Output feedback linearization based torque control of synchronous reluctance motor without mechanical sensor," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol.57, no.1, pp.375-384, Jan.2010.
- [17] J.Matas, M.Castilla, J.M.Guerrero, L.Garcia, and J.Miret, "Feedback linearization of direct driven synchronous wind turbines via a sliding mode approach," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol.23, no.3, pp.1093-1103, May 2008.
- [18] D.E.Kim and D.C.Lee, "Feedback Linearization control of three phase UPS inverter systems," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol.57, no.3, pp.963-968, Mar.2010.
- [19] R.W.Brockett, "Feedback Invariants for non-linear systems," in *Proc. 7th IFAC World Congress*, Helsinki, Jun.1978.
- [20] B.Jakubczyk and W.Respondek, "On linearization of control systems," in *Bulletin de L'academie Polonaise des Sciences*, vol.28, 1980.
- [21] L.R.Hunt, R.Su, and G.Mayer, "Design for multi input non linear systems," in *Differential Geometric Control Theory*, NY: Birkhauser, Proc. Conf., MTU June 28-Jul.2, 1982, pp.268-298.
- [22] Changliang Xia, Qiang Geng, Xin Gu, Tingna Shi, Zhanfeng Song, "Input-Output feedback Linearization and speed control of a surface permanent magnet synchronous wind generator with the boost chopper convertor," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol.59, no.9, Sep., 2012.